

GROWTH AND DEPOSITION OF NICKEL FERRITE THIN FILM

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Abstract:

The thin films of nickel spinel ferrite were deposited on glass substrate using spray pyrolysis deposition technique. The deposited thin films, after annealing were characterized by X-ray diffraction at room temperature in 2θ range of 20° - 80° . Using XRD data the structural parameters as like crystallite size, lattice constant, and X-ray density were obtained and found to be in the reported range. The optical absorbance was recorded in the range of 400-1100nm. Using this data the band gap of the nickel ferrite thin film was calculated.

Keywords: NiFe₂O₄ thin films, Spray pyrolysis, X-ray diffraction, Optical properties

Introduction:-

The applications of thin film ferrite are numerous and require high quality ferrite films at low temperature. In the spinel structure, the relatively large oxygen ions form a close packed FCC lattice with two kinds of interstitial sites, the tetrahedral (A) sites and octahedral [B] sites that are surrounded by four and six oxygen ions respectively. The smaller transition metal cations M²⁺ and Fe³⁺ occupy the interstices of oxygen ion lattice. Among the spinel ferrite, nickel ferrite has received attention of scientist and technologist due to its large magnetic anisotropy and magnetostriction. In the recent years, a nanocrystalline nickel ferrite thin film has been used for gas sensing applications [1]. The crystal structure of nickel ferrite possesses inverse spinel structure with one half of Fe³⁺ ions on (A) site and rest together with Ni²⁺ ions at [B] site at room temperature. A variety of physical as well as chemical methods has been applied for the deposition of cobalt ferrite thin films. Physical methods include pulsed laser deposition [2], sputtering [3] etc. Physical methods have many drawbacks such as small area of deposition, requirement of sophisticated instruments, high working cost of system, wastage of depositing

material, cleaning after each deposition, etc. Keeping drawbacks of physical methods in mind, recently, several chemical methods are used for the preparation of ferrite thin films. On the other hand, chemical methods are simple, economical and convenient for the deposition of metallic thin films. The different preparative parameters are easily controllable. Chemical methods including sol-gel route [4], low pressure chemical vapour deposition [5], electro deposition [6] and so on are considered for the synthesis of spinel ferrite thin films of fascinating magnetic properties [7]. Out of all these chemical methods, spray pyrolysis method is most convenient and suitable for the preparation of spinel ferrite thin films. In the present work, nickel ferrite (NiFe_2O_4) thin film deposited by spray pyrolysis technique and its structural as well as optical properties are presented here in detail.

Experimental and characterizations

Nickel ferrite (NiFe_2O_4) thin film was prepared by spray pyrolysis technique. Analytic reagent grade chemicals as $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were used as starting materials. The two metal nitrate solutions were dissolved separately in de-ionized water at the concentration of 0.1 M for Ni^{2+} and 0.1 M for Fe^{3+} solution. Final solutions were prepared by mixing these two solutions in 1:2 volumetric proportions. Nickel ferrite thin films were prepared by spraying the solution onto previously cleaned glass substrate. The deposited films were characterized by X-ray diffraction method (XRD) and the optical absorption studies were carried out using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Systronics 119) in the wavelength range 300-1000 nm.

Results and discussion

X-ray diffraction

Nickel ferrite thin film deposited on glass substrate was characterized for X-ray diffraction technique in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° . Fig. 1 depicts the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of deposited thin film. The XRD pattern revealed good crystallinity because of annealing of the film. The NiFe_2O_4 film is oriented along (311) plane. The other planes viz. (111), (220), (222), (400), (511) and (440) also exist in the XRD film which was sharp and intense. The XRD patterns matches well with the characteristics reflections of cubic spinel structure. The analysis

of XRD pattern revealed the formation of single phase cubic spinel structured nickel ferrite thin film. The crystallite size was determined from full width of half maximum (FWHM) of the most intense (311) peak using Scherrer's formula [8]. The crystallite size is of the order of 20nm, which indicates the nano-crystalline nature of the film. The value of crystallite size is given in table 1. Using the 'd' value and corresponding Miller indices, the value of lattice constant of the nickel ferrite thin film was evaluated. The value of lattice constant 'a' is given in table 1 which is in good agreement with the reported value [9]. The value of 'a' was used to obtain the unit cell volume, X-ray density, and are given in table 1.

Figure 1: XRD pattern of nickel ferrite thin film

Table 1: Lattice constant (a), Unit cell volume (a^3), crystallite size (t), X-ray density (d_x), $NiFe_2O_4$ thin film.

Structural Parameters	Observed values
Lattice constant	8.3638 Å
Unit cell volume	585.07 Å ³
Crystallite size	20 nm
X-ray density	5.299 gm/cm ³

Optical Absorption

Optical study of nickel ferrite thin film was carried out to investigate the band gap energy of the film. The optical absorbance of annealed thin film was studied in the range 400-1100 nm, using UV-Vis spectrophotometer, which has been further used for the energy band gap calculation. Figure 2 shows the variation of optical absorption with wavelength.

The absorption edge of the nickel ferrite thin film appeared to shift towards the longer wavelength side. The data was analyzed from the reported classical relation [10] for near edge optical absorption in semiconductors which gives relation between the optical band gap, absorption coefficient and energy ($h\nu$) of the incident photon. The variation of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus ' $h\nu$ ' is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2: Plot of Optical absorbance (αt) against wavelength (λ) of NiFe₂O₄ thin film

Figure 3: Plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ against hv for $NiFe_2O_4$ thin film

The value of optical band gap was calculated by extrapolating the straight line portion of graph on 'hv' axis. The obtained band gap value for nickel ferrite thin film was 2.36 eV.

Conclusion

Low temperature deposition of $NiFe_2O_4$ thin film on glass substrate by spray pyrolysis technique was successfully achieved. The annealed nickel ferrite thin film exhibits single phase cubic spinel crystal structure. The crystallite size of the film is of the order of 20nm, reflecting nanocrystalline nature of the film. The optical study reveals the band gap of the value of 2.36 eV.

References

- [1]. C.V. Gopal Reddy, S.V. Manorama, V.J. Rao, Sens. Actuators, B 55 (1990) 90.
- [2]. Y.N. Nuli, Q.Z. Qin, J. Power Sources, 142 (2005) 292.
- [3]. S. Venzke, R. B. Vandover, J. M. Philips, E. M. Gyorgy, T. Siegrist, C. H. Chen, D. Werder, R. M. Fleming, R. J. Felder, E. Coleman, R. Opila, J. Mater. Res., 11 (1996) 1187.

- [4]. P. Lavela, J.L. Tirado, J.Power Sources, 172 (2007)379.
- [5]. J.L. Gunjekar, A.M. More, V.R. Shinde, C.D. Lokhande, J. Alloys and Compounds, 465 (2008) 468.
- [6]. S.D. Sartale, C.D. Lokhande, M.Giersig, V.Ganesan, J. Phys. Condens. Matter, 16 (2004) 773.
- [7]. M.Sultan, R. Singh, J. Mater. Lette., 63 (2009) 1764.
- [8]. C.D. Lokhande, S.S. Kulkarni, Rajaram S. Mane, K.C. Nandi, Sung-Hawan Han, Current Appl. Phys., 8 (2008) 612.
- [9]. A. Guinier, X-ray Diffraction, San Francisco, CA, (1963).
- [10]. J.Tauc, Amorphous and Liquid semiconductors, J. Tauc Edi, New York, Plenum., (1974).